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MARKETING STRATEGY FOR DEVELOPING A SUCCESSFUL SALES PROFILE; ESPECIALLY IN BANKING SECTOR

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ABSTRACT

A marketing person without adequate marketing skills will destroy sales instead of increasing it. Marketing in banking sector needs not only selling skill, but adequate knowledge about banking world also. A good sales person requires right soft skills like positive attitude, good communication etc, and should adhere to the principles like handling objectives, follow up etc. For years the banking services industry has researched over and over again what their customers are looking for. What are the most important attributes to the relationship they have with their customer? What promises would be most likely to attract new customers? The word service is always at the top or near the top of the list. So what did the marketers and ad agencies do? They all claimed to have great service. But that misses the boat. People define service differently.

After the banking sector reforms, marketing has developed as a more integrated function within financial service organizations like banks largely as a result of rapid changes in the operating environment. Banks Marketing is defined as a aggregate of function directed at providing service to satisfy customer’s financial needs and wants, more effectively than the competition keeping in view the organizational objective of the bank. The bank marketing has become a very complex yet interesting subject as it requires the knowledge of economics, sociology, psychology, banking and also core marketing concept.

Key Words: strategy, Sales profile, Banks Marketing, sales person

BANK MARKETING: AN INTRODUCTION

Marketing in most financial institutions including is a new phenomenon. Before that marketing was synonymous with advertising and public relation and role of marketing was more

tactical than strategic. However, due to fierce competition generated by the entry of new generation private sector banks, marketing has become a strategic tool of product promotion and business development, and all the banks whether in public sector or private sector have full-fledged department to effectively put in place all the ‘7Ps’ known as ‘marketing mix’ (a term coined by Kotler) which consists of product, price, place, promotion, people, process and physical evidence. To put in marketing terms, it is not only necessary for a bank to have right product but also to have right price, delivered by right people, using right processes, packaged in right manner and at a right place. The salesperson is the crucial part of marketing mix. Bank Marketing is the aggregate function directed at providing service to satisfy customer’s financial needs and wants, more effectively than the competition keeping in view the organizational objective.

Evaluation in bank marketing

Figure 1.1: Evaluation in bank marketing

Banking Marketing Mix

Figure 1.2: Banking Marketing Mix

ESSENTIALS OF A SALESPERSON

‘People with right soft skills’ are the requirement of marketing. A salesperson should have pleasing personality, attractive mannerism, positive attitude, good communication and negotiation skills and genuine concern for customers’ problems. He should be attractive, smart, simple, serious, outgoing, aggressive, passionate and energetic. He should have high level of energy and abounding self-confidence to win and hold passionate desire to perform. In fact marketing is for fittest, fastest and smartest.

Figure: 1.3

A fit and fast salesperson must know and truly identify himself with his company, know about its product, its customers and its competitors know his responsibilities and should know how to make sales presentations. He should value relationship and follow ethical practices to offer value for money to his customers. A salesperson should remember that the credibility is the essence of marketing and he should never make false claims (regarding quality or delivery schedule). He should be fast enough to respond to customer’s demand and satisfy his queries accurately and promptly. He should be smart enough to greet the customer with smile, treat the customer with all the comfort he expects and meet his product/ service wants and needs.

Describe your businesses:

- Mission statement, corporate vision, and strategic intent.
- Long-term goals and objectives, e.g., profit, ROI, market share, expanding reach into existing set of core customers, or expansion into new markets.
- Organization:
 - Key personnel.
 - Team overview.

- Organizational chart.
- Products and/or services:
 - Value proposition, including the problem your product is solving for customers or the needs your product provides.
 - Key differentiators.
 - Sales trends and profitability (years, seasonality, share of major brands).
 - Pricing overview.
 - Branding.
 - Growth opportunities.
 - Target market.

Need of the Study

The research is to evaluate of the banking sector in India has primal importance due to intense competition, and changing banking reforms. This research is very important because in today scenario there is strong competition in public and private sector banks. It's very important to know which sector is performing well and what are the marketing strategies adopted by banks of public sector and private sector.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study marketing efforts of select public and private sector banks in terms of their market analysis.
2. To make a comparative analysis of marketing systems, procedures and staff of the banks under study.
3. To identify customers preference of banks and analyze reasons for their selection.
4. To analyze the role of 7 Ps framework in formulating marketing strategies of select public and private sector banks and assess its effectiveness in the fulfillment of marketing objectives.
5. To examine the demographic factors of customers and analyze their influence in the selection of banks and their satisfaction level.
6. To evaluate strategies for customer retention and customer loyalty.
7. To develop successful sales profile for the banking sector.

Market Research and Analysis

Gaining information about your target market and key factors that influence customers' buying decisions is typically one of the following:

- Quantitative Research: Statistical and uses mathematical analysis.
- Qualitative Research: Identifies key issues from collected data.

Generally, market research includes:

- Identifying and testing potential target markets.
- Determining ideal customer profile and demographics for your products. – Determining market influences on timing, pricing, service, etc.
- Gauging economy and buyer confidence.
- Conducting competitive analysis.
- Testing perceptions towards brands, companies, images, packaging. – Measuring customer satisfaction and benchmarking satisfaction against competitors.
- Capturing key criteria for your SWOT analysis.

A situation analysis considers internal and external factors that could influence your marketing strategy. Analyzing your strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats (SWOT analysis) is simple, yet powerful, and will help you develop your goals and marketing strategies.

Strengths (Internal): Positive attributes, tangible and intangible, internal to your business that are within your control. What do you do well? What advantages do you have over your competition?

Weaknesses (Internal): Factors within your control that detract from your ability to obtain or maintain a competitive edge, such as lack of expertise, limited resources, inferior service offerings, or the poor business location.

Opportunities (External): Reasons your business exists and prospers and reflect the potential you can realize through implementing your marketing strategies.

Threats (External): Factors beyond your control that could place business at risk and may lead to deteriorating revenues or profits, such as competition, price increases by suppliers, economic downturns, or a shift in consumer behavior.

MARKETING STRATEGIES

Part of the challenge of marketing is determining which distribution method and placement strategy to use for your business.

- **Retail:** Stores selling directly to customer.
- **Wholesale:** Selling to a distributor that sells to retail stores or the customer.
- **Direct or Print Mail:** Generally catalog merchants that sell directly to customer.
- **Telemarketing:** Merchants sell directly to customers at retail via phones.
- **Internet Marketing:** Merchants sell directly to buyers at retail prices, or business-to-business products and services at wholesale prices via the Internet. This also includes social media, such as Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, etc.
- **Sales Force:** Salaried employees or independent commissioned representatives sell products directly to the customer.
- **Advertising:** Internet ads, magazines, sponsorships.
- **Networking:** This includes tradeshows, joining industry organizations, attending industry breakfasts/luncheons.

Principles of Salesmanship – Kotler’s Model

Selling is an art. It pre-supposes that salesperson understands customer’s needs and is competent to offer effective solution to his needs, Salesmanship assumes that

- (a) Customers have latent needs that provide opportunity to salesperson,
- (b) They like suggestions, and
- (c) They will be loyal to the salesperson if he satisfies their long-term interests.

The Kotler’s model of salesmanship comprises the following aspects:

*** Prospecting and Qualifying**

First step in selling is to identify lead, which can be done by

- (a) Asking current customers to tell prospective customers,
- (b) Cultivating sources of potential customers through dealers, distributors, suppliers, trade associations etc,
- (c) Data sources like newspaper, magazine, directories, bulletin etc, to search name, and
- (d) Using telephone and other media to know prospective customers. A sales person should have ability to convert all this information to identify a potential customer.

*** Pre- approach**

Pre- approach means that sales person must learn as much as possible about potential customers’ needs, habits, preferences, personal characteristics, buying styles and buying decision process. It is useful to recall that the Indian market is one where large numbers of prospective customers have very low per capita capacity to save/pay. The innovative way to lure these customers will be to have low cost entry products- opening savings bank account with Rs. 100. He should also decide best approach, i.e., how (personal visit, or telephone or letter), when (time of visit) and where (office or residence) to contact the prospective customer.

*** Approach**

First impression is last impression. Success of a salesperson lies in opening lines and his follow-up remark. The spoken words are most powerful tool that creates sales. Approach is concerned with attitude, manners and appearance of the salesperson and relates to his ability to communicate with the prospective customer. Banks have started spending huge money to train their salespersons to develop their selling skills.

***Presentation**

Presentation signifies conveying product features, benefits and qualities to the prospective buyer so as to stimulate buying. Kotler suggested AIDA formula, i.e. getting attention, holding interest, arousing desire and obtaining action. Sales presentation can be of three types;

(a) Canned approach based on memorized sales talk covering the points about product features. It is based on stimulus response theory that suggests that by proper use of words, pictures, action and terms, salesperson prompts customer to buy the product

(b) Formatted approach also based on stimulus response thinking but lays emphasis on first identifying buyers need and buying style and thereafter approaching him. For example, if the customer is cost conscious type then it is best to offer him low cost or no-frills product.

(c) Need satisfaction approach is based on search of customer's needs. In this approach, the customer is encouraged to come out with his requirement and based on this, product is tailor made to suit his needs/wants. With the introduction of technology, sales presentation has become very scientific and focused which not only saves time and resources of the sales person, but also enables the target audience to understand the product better.

***Handling Objections**

After presentation, customer should be encouraged to raise objection and doubt so that all the objections and doubts are cleared to the best extent possible. Customer raises objections because they may find certain gaps either in their understanding or in the adequacy of information or just the fact that they do not like the marketers. Objections are natural behavioral elements from consumers and cannot be wished away. These objections and doubts can be classified into two categories:

(a) Psychological resistance that includes resistance to interference, preference for existing brands, tendency to resist change, dislike deciding new things, predetermined ideas and unpleasant past experience.

(b) Logical resistance that includes objection or doubt for price, quality, delivery schedule, or product features. It is very important that the objections should be clearly understood and addressed to the best of their satisfaction. For this it is important that the marketers must have thorough product or services knowledge and must communicate the benefits to the consumers. Salesperson should answer all these objections in such a way that all doubts are reasonably clarified and customer is prompted to buy the product. Handling objections is a very tricky business and most difficult part of the salesmanship. Negotiation skills play a major part in handling objections tactfully and firmly. Above all, marketers should always be encouraged and motivated to face challenges, as it will enable them to stay focused and deliver results. In fact, marketer must be a creative learner. He must be willing to experiment and able to learn from mistakes.

*** Closing**

Once presentation is made and objections are satisfied, salesperson should fetch the orders. It is his ultimate object. It is his moment of truth. Closing requires confidence, competence and capability to read closing signals from the customers and decide right timing of obtaining order. Finer details like terms and conditions, repayment period, interest-rate, option fixed or floating etc., should be repeated once again so that there remains no ambiguity. Most selling is persuasive today. In a demand led market where the game. If a salesperson feels that the customer is avoiding or postponing a buying decision, he should tactfully lure him by freebies, discount etc. He can also tactfully say that offer will lapse if not availed or it is lifetime opportunity, which the prospective customer should not miss. He should say ‘thanks’ once the deal is over. Of course, one final advice while closing sale, a sales person should:

- (a) Never feel insulted by the refusal
- (b) Never write-off a customer, and
- (c) Never give up.

*** Follow-up**

It is an exercise of establishing long-term relationship with the customers so that salesman remains in touch with post sales issues and get the repeat orders. For banks, follow-up means to look into personal problems of the customer so that debt is rescheduled or extension in payment is allowed so that there is no technical default. Follow-up also means to provide post credit counseling so that salesperson remains in touch with the customers and exploit the opportunity for cross-selling or up-selling. He can also check that whether the customer is totally satisfied with the product and in case he has any doubt/problem that should be sorted out immediately. So, a sales man should keep on calling his customers to stay in touch, not necessarily to sell more.

Decision Influencer

Although a consumer may get information for a product or service through multiple sources of communication (including 1:1 with salesperson), he/she may at times consults others before taking the buying decision. These persons may be housewives, kids and elders in family (village elders in rural areas). A smart salesperson always remains active and agile to watch such influence by studying and analyzing social and cultural habits that influence the purchase decision. In Indian context, housewives play an important role in decision-making particularly in big-ticket loans like housing, car, insurance etc. Salesperson should be aware of her likes and dislikes so that her concerns are addressed.

Fair Practices Code

Sometime customer complains about too much intrusion in his/her private life by the salesperson like unsolicited telephonic call by Credit Card Company or an insurance agent. With consumer awareness increasing for privacy and RBI insisting on anti-tying measures, banks are putting in place fair practices code for their salesman. These practices include maintaining do not call list, check the frequency of calling per month, seek permission before talking and immediate disconnection if permission is denied, respecting privacy of the customer, identifying hours and day of calling and putting complaint handling process and response time in place. A salesperson should be sensitive enough to draw a limit of intrusion in private in private domain of the customer that may create his/her dislike. A salesperson should follow the fair practices code both in letter and spirit.

Selling to Internal Customers

Fierce competition in banking is post-reform development. In competitive environment, customers can choose what they consider best. In choosing their banks, customers are influenced by the image of the bank and the perceived quality of service. The banks that provide better service or perceived to be better than others get customers. Satisfactory service in itself works like a 'brand' for the bank. It speaks of the service standard. A perception of good service relates to courtesy, promptness, employee attitudes, physical facilities, customers, recognition, speed, clarity and communicative skills and host of such features. It gets manifested in the care, concern, commitment and sensitivity shown by the bank staff. A delighted customer helps the bank in acquiring new customers through word-of-mouth publicity.

Banks have started selling third-party products like insurance, mutual funds, government securities, RBI relief bonds etc. Selling of these products requires marketing skills in employees. Today, as the competition is becoming 'cut-throat' day-by-day, banks have realized that marketing is one and the only way to remain in a business. The challenge before the bank is to make each and every employee-manager an armed guard-as an effective salesperson. This requires a whole lot of selling to internal customers to change their mindset and ramping up belief that marketing is a support function which the whole organization needs in present day banking.

Value Proposition: The New Mantra

Traditional products like fixed-deposits are no longer attractive to customers given the low rate of interest. Wealth management and private banking is fast emerging as lucrative proposition for banks since customers are looking to invest in alternate financial products like insurance and

mutual funds, which give higher yields with tax shield. Since these products come with higher risks, the bank needs to educate customers so that potential investor understands the inherent risk of various products fully. The IEDA AMFI have mandated that the value proposition and risks of insurance and mutual funds products have to be clearly explained by the sales person to prospective investors and for that the salesperson must be duly accredited for selling such products after qualifying/passing the prescribed test. These financial advisors are not mere the salesperson but in true sense they are financial 'guides'.

Scope of the Study

The public sector banks and old private sector banks who command over 80 percent market share in the banking industry must seize this opportunities in big way and respond aggressively to market demand if the growth in banking has to accelerate. So, after awareness of all new challenges and opportunities, banks have to focus on no. of trends like the reach and value that banks offered to customers, its technological convenience, the high cost of intermediation leading to change in progress, yet to gain momentum, consolidation through mergers and acquisitions. To overcome these challenges banks can adopted many marketing strategies like E-banking, product differentiation, reform banks as supermarket, use customer guidelines to form new strategies, use information technology in service sectors and in this regard respondent's opinions were gathered basing upon Visakhapatnam district. It also help to develop a successful sales profile so that banking sector will get the perfect sales personal for their sales work.

CONCLUSION

This article talked about the importance of first impression being the last impression. Success of a salesperson lies in opening lines and his follow-up remark. Banks have started spending huge money to train their salespersons to develop their selling skills. Presentation skills are extremely important as it signifies conveying product features, benefits and qualities to the prospective buyers so as to stimulate buying. After presentation, customer should be encouraged to raise objection and doubt so that all the objections and doubts are cleared to the best extent possible. Closing of the deal and then follow-up take place. For banks, follow-up means looking into personal problems of the customers so that debt is rescheduled or extension in payment is allowed, avoiding technical default.

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